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D7.3 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AB	Advisory Board
ACC	Automotive Cells Company
AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
CID	CIDETEC
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CNRS	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique
FZJ	Forschungszentrum Jülich
IMN	Institut des Matériaux Jean Rouxel (CNRS/Université de Nantes)
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LOM	Lomartov
M1-M12	Month 1 – Month 12
MEET	Münster Electrochemical Energy Technology (Université de Münster)
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
OS	Open Science
POLITO	Politecnico di Torino
R&I	Research and Innovation
SET plan	Strategic Energy Technology Plan
SSB	Solid-state batteries
TNO	Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research
VTT	Technical Research Centre of Finland
WMG	Warwick Manufacturing Group (Université de Warwick)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document traces the strategy for the dissemination and communication activities of the SOLVE project updated on M18. It aims to support the project partners in carrying out appropriate and effective communication activities and ensuring they are conducted in accordance with requirements detailed in the Grant Agreement. This document should be used as a handbook to be accessed frequently by partners to understand the external communication procedures for the project.

It will thus present the following points:

- It describes the overall external communication objectives for SOLVE and the project target audiences and potential key messages.
- It lists and describes the key external communication tools, including visual identity, project website and social media accounts.
- It describes the key external communication activities, including publications, press releases, the link with other EU policies and EU projects as well as the external publications.
- It describes what should be the partners' involvement in the project communication through their social media & website, participation to events, proposals for publications.
- It presents how the project communication and dissemination will be monitored and evaluated through "Key Performance Indicators" (KPIs) and how each partner should report on its communication activities.

This document is therefore a communication plan which allows the implementation of the strategy as defined in the application form.

T7.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

1. THE COMMUNICATION STRATEGY

1.1. REMINDER OF THE PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Solid-state batteries (SSB) offer a promising opportunity for the EU to become an early player and enhance its position in the global battery market.

Supported by a consortium comprised of key industry and academic players in the battery field, SOLVE aims to capitalize on the extensive R&D base and contribute to the scaling-up efforts required for Gen4b mass production.

To this end, SOLVE will address the most significant barriers hindering sector growth by demonstrating innovations across the main stages of the value chain, optimizing active and inactive materials, and associated processing techniques under industrially relevant conditions (TRL \geq 6).

The implementation of novel digital tools and models will reinforce this entire process, supporting and accelerating the cell design process. It will also facilitate the incorporation of imperative sustainability criteria, promoting efficient resource utilisation through eco-design principles and the development of innovative recycling processes.

1.2. REMINDER OF THE COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION OBJECTIVES

The dissemination, use and valorisation of the project results make a crucial contribution in the achievement of the expected outcomes and impacts. It will include activities to raise awareness about how the use of **R&I European funds** contributes to addressing societal challenges, as well as the importance of **R&D** in supporting the decarbonization of the mobility sector. It will also highlight the need to strengthen the relationships between science, industry, and society.

Specific objectives:

- **Community building (M1-M12):** Generation of a community of interested stakeholders. During this phase, messages will focus on informing and generating awareness on the basics: SOLVE's objectives, expected results and impacts, introduction to consortium members, etc.
- **R&D diffusion and cooperation (M12-M36):** As the results of the project emerge, mainly from the second year onwards, dissemination activities will focus on the one-way transfer of project data and outputs to targeted stakeholders. They will also prioritize participation in events and conferences, enabling the active feedback and involvement of stakeholders throughout the research lifecycle. On their end, communication activities aimed to the general public will include information on the main project advancements in easy-to-understand language for non-expert audiences.
- **Exploitation enablement (M24-M48):** Towards the end of the project, dissemination activities will be oriented to support the actual exploitation of project results, reinforcing the visibility and transfer of knowledge to end users, mainly industry, sectoral associations and policymakers.

1.3. COMMUNICATION TARGET

Target audiences: Interests, benefits, and key messages for project's outcomes

(A list of abbreviations is available on page 7).

Universities and research centres: Research institutions will greatly benefit from the project's Open Science (OS) approach, which will enable a wider replication of advances in the SSB technology, multiplying its potential impact, as well as the specific cooperation and dissemination activities targeted towards the scientific community. **Key messages** will emphasize collaboration opportunities to contribute to R&I in SSBs, targeting strong players outside the consortium such as CNRS, CIC Energigune, VTT, TNO, AIT, MEET, FZJ, WMG, IMN, Bluesolutions and others.

Active material providers and processors: Material and component suppliers and producers will benefit from cell component advancements made within the project to access/expand into new markets and experience an increased demand in their product/service portfolio. **Key messages** will focus on highlighting this potential, seeking to attract collaboration opportunities and partnerships for the provision of materials/manufacturing techniques for SSB. Relevant EU actors outside the consortium to be targeted include BASF, UMICORE, IBUtec, ACC, FAAM, Basquevolt among others.

Battery manufacturers and developers among OEMs: SAFT, as SOLVE's main battery manufacturer, stands to gain substantial benefits from the insights generated in the production of SSB. **Key messages** will emphasize the idea of enhanced international market competitiveness and differentiation for SAFT and its associated partnerships (i.e., ACC, AB Members).

System integrators and end-users: Automotive OEMs, represented in the consortium by CRF, will be the main target. OEMs for other mobility applications such as aviation and aerospace will also be considered, represented in SOLVE by PVS. **Key messages** will focus on highlighting these players the enhanced battery performance achieved to attract them to establish potential partnerships and integrate SSB technology into their products. EU automotive players aiming to get into the market with SSB-powered EVs include BMW, Mercedes-Benz AG, FCA Group, PSA Group, Renault and Volkswagen group.

Battery sectoral and cross-sectoral associations: Associations, such as Batteries Europe, European Battery Alliance, Battery 2030+, LiPLANET, UPCCELL, BEPA and BATT4EU etc., serve as crucial gateways to national and European industrial ecosystems within the battery industry and to establish important links for the exploitation and dissemination of the project's innovations. **Key messages** will emphasize the project's significance and relevance to the sector, highlighting how it contributes to the industry's growth and competitiveness. The aim will be to seek close collaboration with these associations and leverage the project's network.

Investors: Verified industrial transferability findings, covering economic and environmental aspects, will help attract private investments for consortium's technology developers from VC firms, angel investors and other sources. **Key messages** aimed at investors will emphasize the project's potential for driving innovation within a rapidly expanding sector, its capacity for market disruption, the competitive advantage it offers, and the potential for attractive financial returns.

Standardization bodies and policy makers: SOLVE products are being developed to reach the objectives defined by the SET plan in terms of performance, reliability, sustainability, and environmental footprint, in line with the expectations of Directive 2006/66/EC and the new Battery Regulation. **Key messages** will focus on interaction with these stakeholders to validate the compliance of SOLVE products with the current and the future EU regulatory framework, and to implement bilateral feedback.

Society at large: Any individual, association, or business with interest in electric mobility. **Key messages** will highlight the project's societal, environmental, and economic impacts, seeking to foster partnerships to drive awareness, education and support. Diverse communication channels will be utilized to effectively reach non-specialized audiences.

1.4. COMMUNICATION STYLE

To provide communication that will reach the targets mentioned above, it was decided to use a consensual style of communication. This decision implied a global analysis in terms of colours, shapes, and graphic inspirations.

The chosen style is minimalistic, highlighting the project's themes and characteristics, and using a range of colours with a pop connotation for modernity, while remaining light and sober on the graphic elements with institutional communication while maintaining a strong graphic bias. The wide range of colours avoids redundancy.

Finally, the graphic identity and the whole SOLVE environment around it must include original elements to stand out in a world saturated by logos and graphic elements that often borrow the same codes.

As far as the message is concerned, it is essential to maintain a serious tone, typical of scientific communication, but this does not prevent the use of original and even amusing tools to stand out from the crowd. In this style of project, however, offbeat communication is out of the question.

2. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

2.1. REMINDER OF EXPECTATIONS

Communication activity	Target audience(s)	KPI
Visual identity	All stakeholders	
The visual identity of the project (logo and brand for all materials) will be designed and created at the beginning of the project. (Ready by M3).		
Website	All stakeholders	1000+ visits/year
A dedicated website, providing both public and private accesses, will serve as a focal point for all the D&C activities. It will provide general information on the project scope and objectives. It will also grant public access to project documents, and to the dissemination activities agenda (seminars, meetings, and conferences). The website, ready by M3, will be maintained during 3 years after the project ends to support the project's impact.		
Social networks	All stakeholders	+ 150 followers/year, +600 interactions/year
Professional and public social networks will be set up at the beginning of the project to maximize the visibility of the published project results, the participation of consortium members to major events and to promote project's organized events.		
Newsletters	All stakeholders	2 newsletter/year
Electronic newsletters containing project updates, news, interviews, and other project-related information will be created. These newsletters will be sent to stakeholders and partner networks as well as uploaded on the project website.		

Printed promotional materials	All stakeholders	Updated each year
Printed promotional materials, like flyers, leaflets, roll-ups, etc. will be formatted by TEN and distributed to project partners upon demand. Partners will be encouraged to ask for these materials and bring them into different events.		
Videos	All stakeholders	2+ videos
Interviews with consortium members to present the project (M10) and main results (M36).		
Press releases	All stakeholders	1 press release/year
Electronic press releases containing project updates, news, interviews, and other project-related information will be created.		

2.2. VISUAL IDENTITY

2.2.1. THE LOGO

Figure 1: SOLVE logo evolution.

The SOLVE logo (**Figure 1**), as originally proposed for the application (opposite left), has been improved to give it more meaning and to tighten up the outline lines and the spacing between the letters and the outline of the battery.

The SOLVE logo is inspired by the shape of a battery, with the 'E' evoking the charge level of the battery. The logo is subject to certain rules of use to ensure that it is legible and recognizable.

For more information, please refer to the deliverable: D7.1 “PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS.”

2.2.2. TYPOGRAPHY

Figure 2: Fractul typography.

The 'Fractul' master typography has been chosen to maintain sufficient originality to stand out from the crowd (**Figure 2**). The lines of this typeface give it a technical feel, with shapes reminiscent of electrical diagrams and lines close to the project's graphics. It will be used for corporate communication, particularly the website's window communication, but also on print communication tools. This typeface will only be used by the communication leader.

Figure 3: Arial typography.

The secondary typeface Arial will be used for all content (**Figure 3**). This font is known for its simplicity and legibility and is the most appropriate for scientific and educational content. A pragmatic typeface that will be used by all members of the consortium. This font also has the advantage of being installed on all computers.

2.2.3. COLOURS

Figure 4: Charter colors.

A palette of colours depicted in **Figure 4** has been defined for SOLVE's visual identity. This limited selection makes it easier to identify and remember the 'brand'. The combination of colours must always ensure good legibility: pastel colours contrast with the two main colours (blue and green), which are sharper. Blue recalls the colour of Europe.

2.2.4. SHAPES

Figure 5: Charter shapes.

Shapes shown in **Figure 5** have been designed for the brand. They are inspired by electrical diagrams, to create a strong and meaningful group identity.

For more information on the project's communication identity, please refer to the deliverable: D7.1 "PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS".

2.3. WEBSITE

As explained above, the website (**Figures 6-9**) should be the showcase for the project. It will be updated as the project progresses. Each member of the consortium can contribute to its content by publishing scientific articles and research results from the project. Visitors can contact the project leaders using a contact form. A contact address: contact@solveproject.eu has been created to receive these requests. CID as coordinator and TEN as communication leader are responsible for collecting requests.

To be able to benefit from a great deal of latitude in the production of content, it has been agreed with the communications agency that almost all the site content can be modified directly within the project by TEN.

Some illustrations of the website interface are shown below. For a more detailed presentation of the website, please refer to the deliverable D7.1 "PROJECT VISUAL IDENTITY, WEBSITE AND SOCIAL NETWORKS ACCOUNTS".

Figure 6: SOLVE website – screenshot of homepage.

Figure 7: SOLVE website - project challenges explained for each stage of the value chain.

Figure 8: SOLVE website - the members of the consortium are presented with links to their websites.

Figure 9: A contact form allows visitors to contact us, send comments and/or ask questions about the project.

2.4. SOCIAL NETWORKS

2.4.1. LINKEDIN

The LinkedIn account of the SOLVE project must communicate the progress of the project intended for an expert, scientific and professional audience. Scientific publications as well as specific dissemination and communication events linked to the project, including updates on project development and project meetings, can be relayed there. LinkedIn is a professional network that highlights expertise and content intended to provide information that can be useful and fuel the debate on ideas. Interactions will be very important and outside ideas welcome.

The tone must remain serious, even if it is possible to offer slightly offbeat content to perform.

LinkedIn campaigns will be planned throughout the project, enabling the consortium members to be introduced in the first year, and then in next years to communicate results, news, and events. From the second year onwards, we have added the dissemination of achieved milestones to provide more scientific content. Publications will be advertised in the most favorable time slots, i.e. Tuesdays and Thursdays around midday.

As communications leader, TEN aims to publish between 20 and 30 posts per year and achieve at least 10+ interactions of reactions per post (**Figures 10 and 11**). CID reviews the posts before publication to ensure the quality and scientific accuracy of the content. CID may also republish posts on the project page concerning solid-state batteries that it deems relevant to share. However, the publication of native posts remains solely at the TEN's discretion.

Figure 10: Examples of posts for the campaign (CID team – left, and Arkema team - right)^{1 2}

Figure 11: Example of post for milestones.³

¹ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/solveproject_solve-energy-storage-activity-7239211084488863745-gUg6?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABOQ5GkB4CYpoYskMi2Dx8VIK7OCPOpbCrE

² https://www.linkedin.com/posts/solveproject_science-innovative-sustainable-activity-7246820549824311296-tl-M?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABOQ5GkB4CYpoYskMi2Dx8VIK7OCPOpbCrE

³ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7368583480286367745>

2.4.2. X

The X page will make it possible to address the media world (journalists) and public authorities, who could function as powerful relay for the project. The publications will be rarer than on LinkedIn, but we will highlight the most valuable information, the major progress of the project illustrated by press releases, likely to interest the media. Up to now, the X account has been used to relay news of interest to the press or influencers. Below is the press release announcing the launch of the project. As a communications leader, TEN has set itself a target of 10 posts per year (**Figure 12**), aiming to capture an interaction of 3+ reactions per post.

Figure 12: Example of post on X. ⁴

2.4.3. YOUTUBE

The YouTube page (**Figures 13 and 14**) should serve as support for other networks. Presentation of videos from the consortium partners and more technical interviews on the progress of the project will be published there. The videos may be published in an offbeat tone or not. To increase the performance of posts on social networks, it is strongly recommended to use short video formats (2 min max) in order to keep the audience captivated by videos until the end.

The YouTube Shorts model (10-30-second-long videos in portrait mobile screen format) can also be used to boost performance. However, this format requires the involvement of the other consortium members, who would need to film themselves in their work environment, and it has been very difficult so far to get them on board with this type of initiative. At the end of the first year, it therefore seems difficult to maintain this ambition and to focus more on content produced by Tenerrdis to promote the members and the progress of the project.

As communications leader, **TEN has set itself a target of 2 videos per year**, down from the initial ambition of 5 videos. This adjustment reflects the heavy reliance on the involvement of other members, who are currently focused on their respective project activities. TEN will aim to achieve 50 views per video, an increase from the initial target of 30 views, based on the strong performance

⁴ <https://x.com/SOLVEprojectEU/status/1828085405914464484>

observed in previous video content.

Figure 13: The YouTube page (screenshot).

Vidéos

Figure 14: 3 videos published on YouTube platform in 2024/2025. ^{5 6 7}

2.5. NEWSLETTERS

The SOLVE's plan is to produce two newsletters every year, which will include the latest project news and results, as well as an announcement of upcoming events. Each member of the consortium will be asked to provide content relevant to its activities. The target will be fed by newsletter subscriptions that can be made from the website. This newsletter can then be relayed by the various members of the consortium to their internal targets. Subscription to the newsletter will be recommended wherever the project is presented to encourage people to follow the project in detail. Newsletter statistics will be closely monitored to adjust the target audience and newsletter content in real time.

This is the proposed structure of the newsletter:

PROJECT NEWS

- General Assembly
- Deliverables
- Publications
- Events where partners participated
- Social networks (published videos, invitation to follow)
- Future project events
- Where you will be able to find us in the next months: future participation in events

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=naLs5zu5-iQ>

⁶ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oSBZBSYnPh0>

⁷ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xz1Nt2EIVTE>

TECHNICAL PERSPECTIVE

- Short introduction about the authors and their institute
- Perspective from one partner about a technical part of the project
 - Suggested topics: SSB, solid electrolyte, cathode, anode, modelling, recycling etc.

OTHER SSB NEWS

- Big announcements of stakeholders
- Upcoming events: conferences, forums, webinars of interest
- Public funding opportunities
- Collaboration opportunities

The first newsletter was prepared at the end of March 2025 (M10) (**Figure 15**). Following its distribution, the website recorded a significant increase in visits (77 sessions in one week compared to an average of 16 in normal times as shown on **Figure 16**).

Figure 15: 1st newsletter mock-up (March 2025).

Figure 16: Number of visits to the SOLVE website.

A second newsletter was distributed on 1st October 2025, focusing more on the end uses of solid-state batteries, thanks to contributions from Pipistrel on aviation and CRF on road mobility.

This newsletter generated less traffic to the website than the first one. The open and click-through rates for the newsletter are quite good (**Figure 17**), but the number of contacts to whom the newsletter is sent remains low (> 200 contacts), which does not amount to many readers once contacts who do not open the newsletter are removed.

There does not appear to have been any follow-up from the other members of the consortium, yet this is essential in order to generate more subscriptions to our newsletters and traffic to our website. TEN will consider how to further engage the consortium on these issues.

Figure 17: Statistics on the second newsletter.

2.6. PRINTED PROMOTIONAL MATERIALS

Several tools were produced by autumn 2024. These materials are used to promote the project at face-to-face meetings (trade fairs, events, and workshops). Above all, it must be eye-catching and powerful. Only communication tools were produced in the first year, the dissemination tools will be produced once the results are published.

2.6.1. L-BANNER

As part of the project, we have produced three L-shaped banners (double-sided roll-ups) which, when placed side by side, are large enough to serve as a backdrop for interviews. Only the front sides have been produced to create this backdrop, and the reverse sides are planned to be produced later in the project, which will be used to disseminate the results as the project progresses. There will be one side for communication and one side for dissemination.

Finally, each of these three roll-ups (**Figure 18**) is designed to be used independently without compromising the message of the project. For the GA meetings at various places across Europe, and for practical reasons, any roll-ups may be reprinted on site to facilitate the logistics of transport.

Figure 18: Roll-up content.

2.6.2. FLYERS

The plan was to produce a 3-part leaflet outlining the project. To make this tool more effective, the idea was to present it standing up and partially folded. The leaflet shown in **Figure 19** has been designed with a drawing of a battery to attract even more attention. The flyers were distributed to each consortium organization during the first GA in Turin (POLITO). Each organization is free to request additional supplies at any time.

Figure 19: Flyer design.

2.6.3. GOODIES

Several goodies were delivered on schedule. The project acquired SOLVE water bottles, which were distributed at the first GA in Turin for consortium members and SOLVE logo stickers (**Figure 20**) were distributed at the second GA in Dresden (IKTS) and may be distributed beyond the members of the consortium.

Figure 20: SOLVE stickers.

2.7. PRESS RELEASES

According to the Grant Agreement, Tenerrdis aims to publish at least one press release per year. To date, a press release has been sent out in English and in the respective languages of the consortium members in mid-June following the launch of the project (**Figure 21**). An article has been published in the *Dauphiné Libéré* on June 25th, 2024, in France following this press release (**Figure 22**). A second press release will be issued at the end of the 2025/2026 academic year with initial dissemination results.

PRESS RELEASE

Funded by the European Union

24/06/2024

SOLVE: A HORIZON EUROPE PROJECT TO DEVELOP THE SOLID-STATE BATTERY FOR THE MOBILITY OF THE FUTURE!

The Spanish research institute CIDETEC Energy Storage will lead a consortium of 16 partners under the Horizon Europe program to deploy Gen4b solid-state batteries for mobility applications on a large scale. A research project with high hopes, as competition from the Asian battery market grows ever stronger.

A consortium of 16 partners met on June 12 and 13 in Donostia - San Sebastian to launch the Horizon Europe project: SOLID-state battery development and production to drive the future of electromobility (SOLVE).

Liquid electrolyte-based lithium-ion batteries (LIB) are considered the most well-established technology for transport electrification and are likely to remain the preferred option in the coming years. However, it is projected that the improvements in this technology will gradually decelerate towards the end of the decade when they approach their theoretical energy density limits. Therefore, it is imperative to diversify the battery technology offer along with the materials used for its production to reinforce Europe's battery industrial backbone.

In this sense, solid-state batteries (SSB) with Li metal anode (LM-SSB, Gen4b) are considered the next major milestone in the industry by policymakers and mobility original equipment manufacturers (OEMs) due to their enhanced intrinsic safety, durability, their potential to improve fast-charging capability and extending driving range through higher energy density.

SOLVE aims to overcome the obstacles to the large-scale deployment of Gen4b solid state batteries for mobility applications. Over the next 48 months, the project will be supported by a consortium of 16 stakeholders across the entire battery value chain, with a special focus on:

- Achieving high-performing, cost-effective and safe Gen4b solid state batteries (Li-metal and anode-free) with nominal capacity of 20 Ah.
- Developing advanced materials and cell components with improved electrochemical performance and enhanced safety.
- Demonstrating highly sustainable, circular manufacturing for the selected advanced materials at Giga-factory scale, in accordance with EU Battery Regulation.
- Reaching an improvement in safety at representative 10-20 Ah cell level and 0.25 kWh mini-module level suitable for mobility applications.
- Disseminating the obtained results and create training activities contributing to the EU Battery landscape.

The project will be led by 16 organizations (companies, universities, research institutes, associations) from 8 European countries: CIDETEC Energy Storage (ES), SAFT (FR), Arkema (FR), Centro ricerche Fiat (IT), Pipistrel (SI), CEA (FR), Puletecon (FI), Accurec recycling (DE), Delfort (AT), Politecnico Di Torino (IT), Tampere korkeakoulu (FI), Fraunhofer IKTS (DE), EMPA (CH), Certikon (CH), Lomartov (ES), Tenerrdis (FR)

cidetec

Fraunhofer

certikon

PIPESTREL

STELLANTIS

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1/2

Figure 21: Press release.

Figure 22: Article in Le Dauphiné.⁸

3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

3.1. REMINDER OF EXPECTATIONS

Dissemination activity	Target audience(s)	KPI
Peer-reviewed scientific publications	Academia, industry research teams	At least 10 peer-reviewed papers
<p>Project partners are expected to submit at least 10 open access articles by the end of the project. Relevant high-impact journals in which to publish these articles may include <i>Nature Materials</i>, <i>Nature</i>, <i>Energy</i>, <i>Advanced Materials</i>, <i>Chemistry of Materials</i>, <i>Energy & Environmental Science</i>, <i>Journal of Power Sources</i>, <i>Electrochimica Acta</i>, <i>Journal of the Electrochemical Society</i>, <i>Batteries & Supercaps</i>, among others. After the project, effects will continue to be assessed using citation-based metrics, targeting Field-Weighted Citation Impact of >1.</p>		
Workshops and webinars	Industry, Scientific community	At least 4 workshops/webinars organised

⁸ <https://www.ledauphine.com/economie/2024/06/25/mobilite-ce-nouveau-projet-europeen-veut-developper-la-batterie-du-futur>

CID and TEN will organize dedicated workshops and webinars within the project's general dissemination strategy (T7.1), as well as part of the specific capacity building activities (T7.5). Whenever possible, these events will serve as bi-directional channels to obtain external input from experts, encourage knowledge transfer and to recruit new end-users to support the project. At least 4 events will be organized during the last 3 years of the project, targeting a minimum audience of 50 attendees each and including roundtables with AB members. The online and hybrid format will be favoured to maximize the impact.

Conferences and events

All stakeholders

Attend at least 8 conferences/year and present in at least 4/year

Efforts will be made to establish links with other EU-funded projects related to the HORIZON-CL5-2023-D2-02-01 topic, as well as relevant ongoing or future projects in the context of the Batt4EU Partnership. Strong focus will be placed to establish cooperation with ongoing projects funded under the calls HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-03, D2-01-05 and LC-BAT-1-2019, many of which involve active participation from SOLVE partners (see Section 1.2.3). Cooperation with other key initiatives such as BEPA, Batt4EU, BATTERY 2030+ and EBA250 will also be sought to expand the project's scope and impact. Furthermore, partners will attend and present at other international events, conferences, and trade fairs to disseminate the project's results. These include, but are not limited to: Advanced Battery Power Conference, BATTERY 2030+ Annual Conference, EUROBAT Forum, Battery Show Europe, Battery & Electrification Summit, International Lithium Battery Meeting, The Electrochemical Society Meeting, International Battery Association Conference, International Symposium on Polymer Electrolytes, and the International Society of Electrochemistry Meeting.

Training activities

Industry, Scientific community

Organisation of 1 summer school

As part of T7.5, CID, in cooperation with the other partners, will coordinate the development of various training activities aimed at both students and the workforce. These activities will include the preparation of e-learning resources, the arrangement of specific workshops and webinars (as mentioned above), and the organization of a 2–3-day summer school for students and young professionals in the SSB field. Cooperation with relevant training activities such as MESC+ and MSCA Innovative Training Networks such as DESTINY and POLYSTORAGE will be sought.

3.2. ACTIVITIES

To guarantee the most relevant dissemination actions, the members of the consortium will help to define them. This will be the subject of a workshop at the General Assembly (GA 01) in Turin, where everyone will be able to put forward their ideas.

Dissemination actions will only be possible once the first results have been obtained, which are not expected until the 2nd year of the project.

Publications in scientific journals should report the results of active work packages. The choice of these journals will have to consider the specificities of these research areas.

Publish >10 peer-reviewed scientific papers in high-impact (Q1, IF >4) open access journals; at least 5 post- project KER joint developments; at least 5 IP-protected research outputs within the project; at least 4 confirmed expressions of interest from industry end-users for KER technology adoption/adaptation secured.

The beneficiaries must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their

results. In particular, they must ensure that:

- at the time of publication, an electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication is deposited in a trusted repository for scientific publications.
- immediate open access is provided to the deposited publication via the repository, under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights; for monographs and other long-text formats, the license may exclude commercial uses and derivative works (e.g., CC BY-NC, CC BY-ND), and
- information is given via the repository about any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the scientific publication. Beneficiaries (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements.

Metadata of deposited publications must be **open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent**, in line with the **FAIR principles** (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable), ensuring they are **machine actionable**. This metadata must include at least the following information: publication details (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue), Horizon Europe funding, and grant project specifics (name, acronym, and number). Additionally, it should specify licensing terms and provide persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved, and—where possible—their organizations and the grant itself. Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output, or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

Only publication fees in full open access venues for peer-reviewed scientific publications are eligible for reimbursement.

The workshops and webinars will be co-piloted by TEN as communication leader for the logistical aspects (registration, platform settings) and the leader of the work package concerned for the content and running of the webinar.

The first workshop is planned for early 2026 and is expected to focus on the theme of “*Components and Interfaces*”, which should cover the following topics:

- *Interfaces: inside the battery*
- *New processes for cathode membranes*
- *HSPE: Polymers and Binders (behaviour, safety handling of them)*
- *Synthesis of active material*
- *Anode-free: Different materials lithiophilic layers*

Three organizations to host this first webinar have been identified: Cidetec, Polito and EMPA, which are working on these topics. The webinar would consist of a two-hour presentation with three speakers from the three organizations, followed by a Q&A session.

Participation in conferences and events may be proposed by members if events in their respective countries seem relevant to them. They will then have to inform the communication leader and the coordinator. This could take the form of purchasing a stand to exhibit at or participating in the animation of a trade show or conference by presenting the project.

Simply going to a trade show to distribute flyers can also be considered, but more as a communication action than a dissemination action.

The first participations in events took place in 2025: at the BATTERY 2030+ Annual Conference in Münster (Germany) on 6th and 7th May, at the 2nd European Symposium on Polymer Electrolytes (ESPE 2) in Uppsala (Sweden) from 9 to 11 June and at Solid4B cluster workshop on “Bridging Policy, Research, and Industry” on 17th September. An opportunity to present posters about the project as shown in **Figures 23, 24 and 25**.

Figure 25: Participation of POL and CID in the BATTERY 2030+ Annual Conference (left) and CID in ESPE 2 (right).

4. COMMUNICATION RULES

Since SOLVE is a transnational project, with 16 partners from 8 EU countries, communication activities will require input from all project partners to ensure that the target audience and key messages are appropriate for their respective regions and activities. The communication and dissemination activities are planned to allow maximum stakeholder input and the widest possible reach across the EU and beyond. The “waterfall effect” will be possible only through continuous interaction between project partners and the direct target and the potential beneficiaries.

To maximize the impact of external communication and to ensure it will reach its goals, a few rules must be set in place:

- Be coordinated: communication activities should be coordinated by TEN as communication leader.
- Be timely – planned communication activities should be linked to key project milestones or activities.
- Ensure the information is accurate.
- Aim at the appropriate target audience.
- Define and use key messages that are of interest to the target audience(s).

4.1. COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES TRACKER

Two files are made available on the project's common server so that the communication and dissemination activities undertaken by the various members of the consortium can be traced. It is essential that each member keeps this table (**Table 1**) up to date and relays each of its activities. A reminder will be sent out each quarter and particular care will be taken to ensure that the table is filled in correctly.

The project partners must always keep the communication leader informed of the dissemination activities undertaken. Communication actions can be envisaged to highlight these actions.

MEDIA APPEARANCES: Please save files such as screenshots of media publications, newsletters, and articles here:							
Project partner	Publishing date	Type of media: Newsletter, Newspaper, Internet portal, TV, radio, podcast,...	Name of media	Title in original language	Title in English	Website link (if available) Please supply a PDF version	Country Country where the activity was reported
TENERDIS	25/06/2024	Internet	Dauphiné Libéré	Mobilité : ce nouveau projet européen veut développer la batterie du futur	Mobility: this new European project aims to develop the battery of the future	https://www.ledauphine.com/economie/2024/06/25/mobilite-ce-nouveau-projet-europeen-veut-developper-la-batterie-du-futur	France
TEMPERE UNIVERSITY	25/09/2024	Internet	Uusiteknologia.fi	EU-rahalla uraauurtavaa akkututkimusta	EU funding for pioneering battery research	https://www.uusiteknologia.fi/2024/09/25/tampereella-tehdään-eu-rahalla-uraauurtavaa-akkuutkimusta/	FINLAND
TEMPERE UNIVERSITY	25/09/2024	Internet	STT Info.fi	Tampereen yliopisto toteuttaa uraauurtavaa akkututkimusta EU-rahoituksella	University of Tampere to carry out groundbreaking battery research with EU funding	https://www.sttinfo.fi/tiedote/70532697/tampereen-yliopisto-toteuttaa-uraauurtavaa-akkuutkimusta-eu-rahoituksella?publisherId=69818730&lang=fi	FINLAND
TEMPERE UNIVERSITY	29/09/2024	Internet	Kemiamedia.fi	Tampereella rakennetaan seuraavan sukupolven akkuteknologiaa –	Tampere is building the next generation of battery technology	https://www.kemiamedia.fi/tampereella-rakennetaan-seuraavan-sukupolven-akkuteknologiaa-	FINLAND

Table 1: Communication activities tracker.

4.2. WEBSITE

Each member can contribute to the content of the website. During the project, members may be asked to contribute feature articles on specific subjects to feed the website and keep it up to date with progress on the project.

4.3. PRESS

As far as possible, consortium partners are expected to relay press releases issued by the communication leader TEN, at least in English, although translation into the partner's language would be preferable.

4.4. SOCIAL MEDIA

SOLVE project posts should be able to be re-shared at least by LinkedIn profiles of project members, and as far as possible by members' company pages.

4.5. COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Each member of the consortium will receive a small pack of flyers at the general meeting in Turin, which they can use as required. If more flyers are needed, it will then be necessary for each member to print them in their own country according to their needs. A digital file ready for printing will be made available.

The three roll-ups produced for the project will be displayed at the various general meetings. Other roll-ups may be produced if the need arises to take part in events. The communications leader should be informed in advance.

5. KPIs REVIEW

COMMUNICATION

Communication activity	Expected target in the Grant Agreement	Target envisaged in the Com & Diss plan	Results	Target for next year
Visual identity	Ready by M3		Reached	
The visual identity of the project (logo and brand for all materials) will be designed and created at the beginning of the project. (Ready by M3).				
Website	+ 1000 visits/year		700	+ 1000 visits/year
In its first year, the website received 700 visits, but the site only went live during the year, with statistics only being recorded from October 2024 onwards. Furthermore, as dissemination has not yet begun, opportunities to visit the website are still rare. The target of more than 1,000 visits remains unchanged for next year.				
Social networks	+ 150 followers/year, +600 interactions/year		360 followers 1118 interactions	+ 150 followers/year, +600 interactions/year
Target greatly exceeded on LinkedIn. The launch of the project prompted numerous LinkedIn posts introducing the partners, generating a lot of interaction and subscriptions. In the second year, there is a risk of reaching a plateau with fewer posts, as dissemination is only just beginning. Ambitions will therefore remain aligned with the expectations of the Grant Agreement. Activity on X remains focused on news of major importance that may be of interest to the media.				
Newsletters	1 newsletter/year	2 newsletters/year	2 newsletters/year	2 newsletter/year
The newsletter has increased the number of visits to the website, demonstrating real interest.				

COMMUNICATION

Communication activity	Expected target in the Grant Agreement	Target envisaged in the Com & Diss plan	Results	Target for next year
Printed promotional materials	Update each year		Reached	Updated each year
Water bottles and stickers were distributed in 2024 and 2025. 1 roll-up banner reprinted for Dresden (GA 02).				
Videos	2 videos for all the project	5 videos/year	3 videos	2 videos
Three videos were produced this year: two during the general assemblies and one during a visit to the CEA. The aim of the five videos proposed for the first year was to rely on the active participation of consortium members, who were to film themselves presenting their laboratories. The project was somewhat ambitious given everyone's workload. We believe it would be preferable to return to a more reasonable target, which would still exceed the ambitions set out in the Grant Agreement.				
Press releases	1 press release/year		1 press release/year	1 press release/year
First press release published in June 2024. A second will be issued in the first half of 2026. One press coverage in <i>Dauphiné Libéré</i> in France.				

DISSEMINATION

Dissemination activity	Expected target in the Grant Agreement	Target envisaged in the Com&Diss plan	Results	Target for next year
Peer-reviewed scientific publications	At least 10 peer- reviewed papers		Not yet	
It is still a little early for scientific publications. Information on the expected publications has been sent to the consortium partners.				

DISSEMINATION

Dissemination activity	Expected target in the Grant Agreement	Target envisaged in the Com & Diss plan	Results	Target for next year
Workshops and webinars	At least 4 workshops/webinars organized		Not yet	1 early 2026
1 webinar planned for early 2026 (see webinar section).				
Conferences and events	Attend at least 8 conferences/year and present in at least 4/year		Present in 3 events	
BATTERY 2030+ Annual Conference 2 nd European Symposium on Polymer Electrolytes (ESPE 2) Bridging Policy, Research, and Industry.				
Training activities	Organization of 1 summer school			A winter school scheduled for 2026 or 2027

6. PLANNIFICATION (2025-2026)

Figure 26: Agenda for communication & dissemination activities.

T7.2 COLLABORATION WITH EU INITIATIVES/PROJECTS AND STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT

1. IDENTIFICATION OF THE TARGET GROUP

A mapping exercise has been conducted to identify the key stakeholders of the SSB value chain in Europe, led by TEN with the support of CID and inputs from the whole consortium. The complete mapping is available to the SOLVE partners in the Share Point and its results will be shared with the community through the project website and social media posts.

In the mapping, made on an Excel file (**Table 2**), there are five tabs:

- In the first one “Initiatives and EU Networks”: there is a list of the EU networks and alliances in the sector of Solid-State Batteries. Most of the project partners are already members of those initiatives and they are good entry points for project results dissemination, to organize common events and to explore exploitation options.
- The second tab entitled “Projects” lists the EU-funded projects focused on the SSB development. They are mostly Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 projects. Overall, 26 projects have been identified in the last six years. This work was useful to identify the key actors of the SSB sector.
- The third tab, “List of actors Europe” lists all the partners in the EU projects identified in the previous tab. They are also classified by typology (University, Industry, Research Center, SME, and others) as well as their position on the value chain (raw materials and active materials providers, component and cell manufacturers, batteries integrators and end users, second life and recycling, consultancy). Their affiliation to any network identified in tab 1 has also been listed.
- The fourth tab “Summary actors Europe” is a summary of the previous slide, mainly in order to show the relevance of each actor. The “Impact” column is calculated on the number of projects they are partners in and the number of projects they are leading. It was decided to factor that being partner in a project counted as 1 and being a lead partner (coordinator) in a project counted as 2. It is based on these numbers that map, and value chains figures will be prepared.
- The last tab “other actors”, aims to identify other actors, based in the EU or not which are working in the SSB value chain.

Name	Country	Number of Projects	Among which Lead ?	Impact	Typology	Value chain	Value chain 2
AALTO	Finland	1	0	1	University	Raw, inactive and active materials	Components and cells
ABEE	Belgium	8	3	11	Industry	Module and pack	Components and cells
ACCUREC Recycling GMBH	Germany	4	0	4	Industry	Second life, environmental analysis and recycling	
AGC Glass Europe	Belgium	1	0	1	Industry	Raw materials and active materials providers	
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas	Spain	3	1	4	Research Center	Raw, inactive and active materials	Components and cells
AIT	Austria	6	2	6	Research Center	Components and cells	Module and pack
Aksoz Kesintisiz Guc Kaynagi Danismanlik Ticaret Sanayi Limited Sirketi	Turkey	1	0	1	Other	Consultancy	
Altris AB	Sweden	1	0	1	SME	Components and cells	
Ampere	France	1	0	1	Industry	Batteries integrators and end users	
Andritz Sovema	Italia	1	0	1	Industry	Components and cell manufacturing	
Aristotelio Panepistimio Thessalonikis	Greece	1	0	1	University	Raw, inactive and active materials	
Arkema	France	3	0	3	Industry	Raw, inactive and active materials	
Armor Battery Films	France	2	0	2	SME	Components and cells	

Table 2: Extract of the Excel mapping.

The data collected will be updated throughout the project to stay relevant and to be able to identify new actors and any news concerning the value chain.

This mapping is part of T7.1 and T7.2 as the necessary basis for dissemination and communication, as well as the collaboration with EU initiatives and projects, including stakeholder engagement. It will also allow the partnership to elaborate a precise SSB value chain of the EU actors.

The next steps are to collectively identify the most relevant actors with whom to elaborate dissemination activities during the project's lifetime and to organize events to gather contributions from experts on SOLVE's results. Then to organize those activities.

Two graphs were produced to make the Excel file more visual: a diagram listing the actors in the value chain (Figure 27) and a map showing their location by country (Figure 28).

Figure 27: Number of actors present in the value chain.

Figure 28: Number of actors by country.

2. MEMBER OF THE SOLID4B CLUSTER

In 2024, SOLVE joined the SOLID4B cluster to improve collaboration between the various SSB projects and increase opportunities for joint action (Figure 29).

Figure 29: LinkedIn post announcing the arrival of the SOLVE project within the SOLID4B cluster (left) CIDETEC's participation in the SOLVE project during an initial webinar organised with SOLID4B (right).^{9 10}

A first webinar was held as part of this collaboration, featuring a presentation by SOLVE coordinator Andriy Kvasha on the topic: “Challenges and Opportunities in High-Energy Li-Metal Solid-State Pouch Cell Development”.

⁹ https://www.linkedin.com/posts/solveproject_solve-solid4bcluster-solidstatebatteries-activity-7262781326099947522-u1Cp?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop&rcm=ACoAABO05GkB4CYpoYskMi2Dx8VIK7OCPOpbCrE

¹⁰ <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7374757195604844544>

7.5 SKILL DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY

During the initial period of the project, CID focused, with the contribution of all the SOLVE consortium, on elaborating skill development strategies through the organization of a summer school with a duration of 3 to 5 days. The details of this training activity were discussed in a dedicated workshop during the General Assembly (GA 02) in Dresden.

This summer school is planned for the period of 2026 – 2027 and will be open to MSc students and early-stage researchers (PhD students and post-doctoral researchers) working in the field of SSB and related topics. The SOLID4B cluster will be the main target audience.

Experts in SSB technologies will be invited as keynote speakers, contributing to a session of an overall duration of approximately four hours. The event will consist of a crash course of 10 to 12 lectures, followed by a roundtable discussion focusing on career development. It will also include interactive sessions with Slido tests as well as a panel discussion in which SSB experts will answer questions from the audience. An outlook on SSB technologies will also be provided.

The event will be promoted on the LinkedIn account of the SOLVE project as well as on other relevant social networking platforms.

The main topics addressed in the summer school are listed below:

- Basic knowledge of SSB
- Comprehensive comparison between LIB and SSB technologies (advantages and challenges)
- Critical aspects of SSB technologies
- SSB examples (e.g., cells, electrodes, types)
- Relevant processes
- Relevant characterization techniques
- Raw materials
- Battery components
- Life cycle assessment (LCA) on SSB
- SSB end users
- Hands-on experience on SSB
- State of the art of battery market – GWh/scale
- Aircraft/space applications
- Road transport applications

A tentative agenda for the summer school for a duration of three days is provided below:

Day	Topic
1	Fundamentals on SSB
2	Main SSB technologies
3	Companies & end users with interest in SSB

CONCLUSIONS

This report D7.3 is the first update of the D7.2 related to WP7, providing an initial review of the strategy. Several adjustments will be made this year to best achieve the objectives set.

This document is used both by TEN to plan the current strategy as effectively as possible and to report on the project's progress in terms of communication and dissemination, and by the other members of the consortium to help them participate in the required efforts. It also summarizes what is expected of them. It is one of the reference documents that will enable the project to move in the right direction and ensure that ongoing actions are carefully monitored and conducted.

TEN, as the communications manager, is available to each consortium member to respond to these needs. The communications manager must use their expertise to ensure effective communication. Each member is free to make suggestions. It serves as a support for consortium members to help support their participation in communication and dissemination efforts. It also summarizes what is expected from them. It is one of the reference documents that will enable the project to evolve in the right direction and ensure that ongoing actions are thoroughly monitored and accomplished.

REFERENCES

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2. X page link: <https://x.com/SOLVEprojectEU>
3. YouTube page link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdPaxiEAqJxENTQF6bVGAhg>
4. Website link: www.solveproject.eu

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